

POTATO CLUSTERS AND COOPERATIVES

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Annotation: *In the context of the crisis caused by the coronavirus pandemic in our country, there are ample opportunities for the effective use of public lands, harvesting up to two or three times a year. This, of course, requires the development of new projects in agriculture and their implementation. This article discusses one such project is potato growing clusters and cooperatives in agriculture.*

Keywords: *land, agriculture, potato cultivation, clusters and cooperatives, market economy, industrial enterprises, farming, seed potatoes, consumer potatoes, land service.*

Introduction: First of all, it should be noted that 80-85% of potato products consumed in the country are grown on farmland.

In this regard, a number of decisions have been made in recent years on the effective use of land, the establishment of the Council of Farmers, Farmer Farms and Landowners of Uzbekistan and its territorial divisions, 244 enterprises "Land service".

Today, the Council of Farmers, Farmer Farms and Landowners of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with relevant organizations, is studying the situation with the planting of crops in the regions. "Land service" LLC, established in the districts, provides practical assistance in planting, caring for, harvesting and selling crops, depending on soil and climatic conditions and water supply.

The council, together with local governors, is digging artesian wells in neighborhoods with poor water supply and focusing on increasing potato production for yield, consumption and seed. In particular, over the past four months of this year, the Fund under the Council has allocated 1 billion 11 million soums in loans to 81 landowners, 1 billion 50 million soums to 35 farms in Gallaaral district of Jizzakh region, 3 billion soums to "Yangikurgan Potato Center Land Service" LLC in Yangikurgan district of Namangan region for the purchase of seed potatoes and the development of potato growing.

It should be noted that 80-85% of the potato products consumed in the country are grown on farmland. In the early spring of this year, potatoes were planted on 45,000 hectares of farmland. At present, in Surkhandarya region, fairy-tale potatoes are being dug up and put into consumption.

The recent resolution "On measures to expand the cultivation of potatoes and further develop seed production in the country," signed by the President, will undoubtedly accelerate the work in this direction. According to the resolution, potato clusters and cooperatives will be established in Uzbekistan, districts and regions will be specialized in potato growing, and a number of innovations and benefits in the field of potato will be introduced. Until July 1, 2023, imported seed potatoes will be exempt from customs duties.

At the same time, potato clusters and cooperatives will be established in districts specializing in potato growing. At the same time, the introduction of advanced technologies, know-how and resource-saving technologies in the cultivation of consumer and seed potatoes, meeting the domestic market demand for consumption and seed potatoes, as well as expanding its exports will be one of their main activities.

The resolution also envisages the specialization of districts and regions for the consumption and cultivation of seed potatoes, including its super elite, elite generations. From May 1 this year, potato farms, agricultural enterprises, as well as potato clusters and cooperatives will be provided with commercial loans for up to 12 months to finance the purchase of seed potatoes.

Conclusion: The resolution of the head of state also set a number of tasks in the field of application of scientific developments in the industry, selection, seed production. The goal is to increase the consumption and production of seed potatoes in the country, to expand the mechanisms of clusters and cooperation in the field of potatoes, and to fully meet the domestic market demand for potatoes. After all, if we do not work today to make our table full, our markets full of goodies and cheap, tomorrow will be too late. Further improvement of the use of scientific and technical achievements in the agricultural sector is also a factor leading to the efficient use of labor resources. The main focus is on the creation of new and high-yielding varieties, the organization of clusters and cooperatives, their introduction into production, the expansion of arable land, taking into account the biological characteristics of potatoes and the demand of the population for it. Taking into account the above, it should be noted that the part of the labor force engaged in the economy is the economically active population. In other words, after deducting from the actual number of labor resources the number of people of working age who are studying separately from production and serving in the military, the rest is the active population. This will lead to the creation of potato clusters and cooperatives, as well as ways to increase production efficiency.

REFERENCES:

1. *A. Abduganiyev. Agricultural Economics. Textbook - T.: 2004.*
2. *Gulomov S. S., Akhmedov D. K., Boyev H. N. Basics of small business and entrepreneurship. T.: 1996.*
3. *Jorayev A. S. et al. Analysis of investment projects. Textbook. - T.: Sharq. 2003.*
4. *Jorayev F. Organization of production at agricultural enterprises. Textbook. "Istiqlol" T.: 2004.*
5. *President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on Wednesday, May 6, signed a decree "On measures to expand potato production and further develop seed production in the country."*